

Best practice approaches to social prescribing in European Primary Care: A Delphi protocol focused on link workers

*Ferdinando Petrazzuoli^{1,2,A-F}, *Josep Vidal-Alaball^{3,4,A-F}, Joyce Kenkre^{5,4,A,D-F}, Thomas Kloppe^{6,4,A-F}, Sinah Evers^{4,A,D-F}, Hendrik Napierala^{7,4,A,D-F}, Jean-Pierre Jacquet^{8,4,A-F}, Wolfram J. Herrmann^{7,4,A,D-F}, Natasa Mrduljaš-Đujić^{9,2,A,D-F}, Andrea Neculau^{10,2,D-F}, Katerina Javorska^{11,2,A,D-F}, David Halata^{11,4,A,B,E,F}, Miriam Dolan^{12,4,A,D-F}, Joanne Robins^{4,A,D-F}, Patrick Ouvrard^{4,A,D-F}, Juan Manuel Mendive^{13,4,A,D-F}, Carmen López Fando^{4,A,D-F}, Jane Randall-Smith^{4,A,D-F}, Erwin Rebhandl^{14,4,A,D-F}, Sara Paternoster^{15,A,B,D-F}, Hans Thulesius^{1,2,A,D-F}, Sian Brand^{16,A,D-F}, Gindrovel Dumitra^{17,4,A,B,E,F}, Donata Kurpas^{18,2,A,D-F}

- ¹ Department of Clinical Sciences in Malmö, Centre for Primary Health Care Research, Lund University, Sweden
- ² European General Practice Research Network (EGPRN)
- ³ Research and Innovation Unit in Primary Care of Central Catalonia, Catalan Health Institute/Jordi Gol Institute for Primary Care Research (IDIAPJGol)/Fundació Institut Universitari per a la Recerca a l'Atenció Primària de Salut Jordi Gol i Gurina, Manresa, Spain
- ⁴ World Organization for Colleges, Academies and Associations for General Practitioners (WONCA) Europe Social Prescribing and Community Orientation Special Interest Group, Paris, France
- ⁵ Life Sciences and Education, University of South Wales, Cardiff, UK
- ⁶ Department of General Practice and Primary Care, University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Germany
- ⁷ Institute of General Practice and Family Medicine, Charité – Universitätsmedizin, Corporate Member of Freie Universität Berlin and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
- ⁸ French College of General Practice, Paris, France
- ⁹ Department of Family Medicine, University of Split, Specialist's Family Medicine Office Postira, Croatia
- ¹⁰ Department of Fundamental, Clinical and Prophylactic Sciences, Transylvania University of Braşov, Romania
- ¹¹ Department of Preventive Medicine, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Czech Republic
- ¹² Department of General Practice, Medical School Queen's University Belfast, UK
- ¹³ La Mina Primary Care Academic Centre, Catalan Health Institute and Institute for Primary Health Care Research IDIAP Jordi Gol, Barcelona, Spain
- ¹⁴ Institute of General Practice, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria
- ¹⁵ Healthcare Trust of the Autonomous Province of Trento, Italy
- ¹⁶ Department of Sport and Health, Writtle University College, Chelmsford, UK
- ¹⁷ Department of Family Medicine, University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Craiova, Romania
- ¹⁸ Division of Research Methodology, Department of Nursing, Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Wrocław Medical University, Poland

A – research concept and design; B – collection and/or assembly of data; C – data analysis and interpretation;

D – writing the article; E – critical revision of the article; F – final approval of the article

Advances in Clinical and Experimental Medicine, ISSN 1899–5276 (print), ISSN 2451–2680 (online)

Adv Clin Exp Med. 2025;34(9):1589–1595

Address for correspondence

Ferdinando Petrazzuoli
E-mail: ferdinando.petrazzuoli@gmail.com

Funding sources

This work was supported by the European General Practice Research Network (EGPRN) under grant No. 2024/59 (www.egprn.org).

Cite as

Petrazzuoli F, Vidal-Alaball J, Kenkre J, et al. Best practice approaches to social prescribing in European Primary Care: A Delphi protocol focused on link workers. *Adv Clin Exp Med.* 2025;34(9):1589–1595. doi:10.17219/acem/208216

Conflict of interest

None declared

* Ferdinando Petrazzuoli and Josep Vidal-Alaball contributed equally to this work.

DOI

10.17219/acem/208216

Received on May 2, 2025
Reviewed on May 30, 2025
Accepted on July 13, 2025

Copyright

Copyright by Author(s)
This is an article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported (CC BY 3.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>)

Published online on August 1, 2025

Abstract

Introduction. Social prescribing (SP) is an innovative model that connects individuals to non-clinical community resources. However, its uptake and evaluation have been hindered by inconsistent role definitions for key stakeholders. Although recent studies have refined SP definitions, outside the UK, the responsibilities, educational backgrounds and training requirements of social prescribing link workers (SPLWs) remain poorly defined. Additionally, it is essential to identify which patient populations will benefit most from SP, establish specific methodologies, and standardize assessment tools and referral pathways.

Materials and methods. We will employ a 3-round Delphi protocol with an international expert panel to establish consensus on SP definitions. Approximately 60 participants from diverse disciplines and regions will be recruited to complete multiple survey rounds, providing insights into the roles of SPLWs, beneficiary populations, methodologies, and assessment tools. Consensus will be defined as at least 80% agreement on a 5-point Likert scale. Data collection and analysis will follow rigorous protocols to ensure validity, reliability and transparency, in accordance with the Guidance on Conducting and REporting DElphi Studies (CREDES) guidelines.

Objectives. The aim of this research is to unify the fragmented understanding of SP and the role of SPLWs, thereby establishing a foundation for integrating SPLWs into healthcare systems where appropriate. The Delphi technique offers key strengths – namely, participant anonymity and structured iterative feedback – to enable robust consensus building. While we acknowledge limitations such as potential participant attrition and the resource-intensive nature of the methodology, these will be mitigated through targeted engagement strategies and strict adherence to established best practices.

Conclusions. This study addresses critical gaps in SP engagement, conceptual understanding and implementation. The anticipated outcomes will reinforce SP's role in community-based, integrated care to reduce health inequalities and foster social cohesion across Europe and beyond. Ultimately, this work aims to enhance the uptake and adoption of SP in primary care.

Key words: primary health care, integrated care, social prescribing, link workers, community health services

Highlights

- Social prescribing (SP) connects patients to community resources – an innovative non-clinical approach that boosts health outcomes and wellbeing.
- Variation in SP definitions and roles across Europe – the absence of standardized personnel guidelines impedes consistent implementation within European healthcare systems.
- It is crucial to clarify the social prescribing link worker (SPLW) role and training – defining educational requirements and competencies is essential for professionalizing SP delivery.
- Targeted SP strategies require clear patient selection, methodologies and assessment tools – identifying who benefits most and how to measure outcomes will maximize SP effectiveness.

Introduction

Social prescribing (SP) represents an integrative approach within healthcare systems aimed at addressing social determinants of health through non-clinical interventions. Primarily delivered through referrals in primary care, SP addresses social determinants of health that are often beyond the scope of traditional biomedical interventions. This is by integrating health and social care with community activities. Social prescribing facilitates patient engagement in health-related decision-making and self-management.^{1–5}

Social prescribing involves directing individuals to activities that align with their social, emotional and physical needs as well as providing social counseling to address social problems. These include, e.g., walking, gardening, cooking, crafting, fieldwork, beekeeping, group learning, and/or sports.⁶ While these activities have historically been integral to European community life, their health benefits are not always formally recognized. However, as SP gains traction across Europe, implementation varies

significantly, shaped by country-specific healthcare systems and infrastructure.

England has pioneered SP, embedding it into its UK National Health Service (NHS) Long Term Plan as a central component of personalized care.⁷ This model emphasizes the role of link workers,⁸ who collaborate with patients to co-design individualized plans connecting them to local initiatives.^{9–18} Similarly, Wales has integrated SP into its Well-being of Future Generations Act, promoting a holistic approach to health.¹⁹

Despite its potential, SP faces challenges across Europe. Variability in program design and funding, limited integration with healthcare systems and uneven European awareness hinder its widespread adaptation. Countries like Italy and Croatia, where SP remains underdeveloped, show the need for systemic support and standardized frameworks.²⁰ Moreover, while SP demonstrates potential in improving mental health, reducing healthcare utilization and advancing community engagement, robust evidence on its long-term efficacy remains scarce.²¹ This lack of evidence

complicates efforts to quantify SP's impact and optimize its implementation.

Many countries struggle to establish systematic connections between healthcare and social systems. In Romania, although governmental and non-governmental organizations provide support to vulnerable populations, a formal referral system, such as SP, has not yet been established.²²

In Spain, Catalonia's SP framework, rooted in primary care and the Health Assets model, has demonstrated the potential to adapt SP to diverse healthcare contexts.²³ In Germany, Herrmann et al.²⁴ have identified significant barriers to implementing SP within the German healthcare system.

The need to tackle these challenges has become more urgent due to the growing prevalence of chronic diseases, mental health issues and social isolation across Europe. The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the importance of community-centered approaches, as it worsened loneliness and disconnection. Social prescribing offers a structured approach to linking medical care with social and community-based services that prioritize comprehensive, patient-centered solutions addressing the full spectrum of health determinants.²⁵

The World Organization for Colleges, Academies and Associations for General Practitioners (WONCA) Europe Social Prescribing and Community Orientation Special Interest Group (SPCO SIG) recognizes the potential of SP in advancing integrated care.²⁶ Leveraging their expertise in rural health and community engagement, the group seeks to clarify the SP concept and the role of social prescribing link workers (SPLWs), map existing SP programs and identify best practices for implementation across diverse healthcare systems.

This study seeks to advance the understanding of SP by identifying key elements that support its development and integration into contemporary healthcare systems. By addressing health inequalities, improving patient outcomes and strengthening community cohesion, SP has the potential to significantly contribute to the implementation of integrated and equitable models of primary care across Europe.^{26,27} The project is led by members of the SPCO SIG under the auspices of WONCA Europe, with support from colleagues in the European General Practice Research Network (EGPRN). The initiative has been awarded a research grant from the EGPRN.

Objectives

This study aims to reach expert consensus on 3 key areas: 1) the target populations most likely to benefit from SP; 2) the methodologies and assessment tools used to evaluate SP outcomes; and 3) the role, qualifications and training requirements of SPLWs.

Materials and methods

Study design

A 3-round Delphi study will be conducted to identify the key elements contributing to the success of SP programs within European primary care settings, as recognized by European experts.

The Delphi technique will be used as a structured method of achieving consensus among experts. This method involves multiple rounds of surveys, where experts respond to questions anonymously. After each round, participants receive feedback summarizing the group responses, allowing them to refine their input in subsequent rounds. This iterative process facilitates the convergence of opinions, enabling the development of agreed-upon definitions and frameworks.

Widely regarded as a robust approach in health science research, the Delphi method is particularly suited to addressing complex topics, such as SP, where diverse perspectives must be synthesized to establish consensus. This study design ensures systematic and comprehensive exploration of the critical factors underlying successful SP implementation in Europe.

This study will be conducted between April 2025 and August 2025. Given the importance of the online survey platform's quality to this study's success, we carefully reviewed and tested several different options before selection. We will use Welphi (www.welphi.com), which is an online survey platform that is designed explicitly for Delphi studies. The Welphi team will make coding changes when necessary to ensure that the online survey platform meets the needs of this study.

Before the start of each round, we will complete the survey development and perform pilot testing. Participants will receive a notification email 10 days before the launch of each round. At the start of each round, participants will receive an email with a link to the survey and a link to a calendar with the details of the round.

Participants will have 2 weeks to complete each round. Each survey will begin with a welcome page, which provides an overview of the survey, describes the data analysis procedures, explains what kind of feedback will be provided at the start of the next round, highlights the aim of the study, and outlines essential information about conceptual and operational definitions to ensure that there will be a common understanding of these terms. Participants will be able to return to the survey as often as they like until the round's closure – their progress will be saved if they leave the study and return later. Even after completing the survey, they can change their submission until the round closes. Each survey will take approx. 15 min to complete. Non-responders will be removed from the study.

Participants

Delphi studies have no universally agreed-upon definition of what constitutes an expert, making participant selection a critical aspect of the research.^{28–31} For this study, experts will be identified based on the following criteria: Individuals involved in the SP and Community Orientation Network, the Global Social Prescribing Alliance or the National Academies for Social Prescribing; authors of academic or grey literature related to SP, even if not explicitly labeled as such; researchers or healthcare providers engaged in SP activities; link workers facilitating SP, regardless of the terminology used to describe their role; patients with experience in SP; or healthcare administrators or managers overseeing the implementation of SP initiatives. The study will be conducted in English. Regarding the panel size, the literature on Delphi studies in health sciences suggests an average of approx. 40 participants, with typical ranges spanning 20–60 experts.^{28–31} This study will recruit approx. 60 participants, ensuring adequate representation from across European countries to achieve a meaningful consensus.

Recruitment

The recruitment process for the study will commence in November 2024 with the opening of the registration survey for members of the SPCO SIG under WONCA Europe. The steering group will develop a comprehensive list of experts from each country based on their expertise in SP, and invitations will be sent to these individuals via email. Publicly available sources will be used to gather contact information.

An international, multidisciplinary panel of experts will be prioritized, ensuring diversity in country, job title, SP expertise, and years of experience. A monitoring system will track recruitment to identify and address underrepresented groups. To this end, targeted invitations will be extended through relevant communication channels, including the Social Prescribing Network newsletter, the Social Interventions Research and Evaluation Network listserv, and the Canadian Social Prescribing Community of Practice listserv. Invitations will also be advertised on social media platforms like X (Twitter) and LinkedIn. Following the principles of snowball sampling, experts will be encouraged to share the recruitment call with their contacts.

Experts invited to participate will receive an email containing a link to the registration survey. The survey's first page will feature an information letter outlining the study's objectives and emphasizing that participation is voluntary. By proceeding beyond this page, experts will provide their informed consent. Consent will be ongoing and voluntary.

The registration survey will collect sociodemographic data, including the participant's name, email address, country, job title, organization, expertise in SP, and years of experience in the field. Once sufficient experts have

registered, participants will be notified about the start of the study's first round. The recruitment process will ensure a robust and representative panel of experts to achieve meaningful consensus on the topics of this study in European primary care settings.

Consensus

Without standardized guidelines for defining consensus in Delphi studies, this study will adopt a widely accepted threshold of $\geq 80\%$ agreement as the criterion for consensus. Participants will indicate their level of agreement on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = "Strongly disagree", 2 = "Disagree", 3 = "Neutral", 4 = "Agree", and 5 = "Strongly agree". An item will achieve consensus if at least 80% of participants select "Agree" (4) or "Strongly agree" (5). This rigorous threshold aligns with best practices in health science research, where consensus is typically defined at levels of $\geq 70\%$, $\geq 75\%$ or $\geq 80\%$, with the latter representing the most stringent level of agreement.^{28–33}

Rounds

The study will include 3 rounds, reflecting the structure commonly employed in Delphi studies. This format is based on prior research demonstrating that most Delphi studies to establish agreed definitions are conducted in 3–5 rounds.^{34–37} Each round will refine and build upon the findings of the previous one, progressively working towards consensus among participants.

Data collection

The Delphi surveys will span 7 months. To ensure confidentiality and impartiality, participants will be assigned randomly generated participant codes by the online survey platform. These codes will not be shared with participants, nor will the research team have a key to link participants to their codes. This anonymization safeguards the integrity of responses and mitigates potential bias.

The study's online survey platform has been carefully selected to facilitate seamless data collection and management while ensuring participant anonymity throughout the study. The anonymized approach will foster an environment conducive to candid and unbiased input, supporting the study's objective of achieving robust expert consensus on SP in European primary care settings.

Round 1 will be conducted in April 2025, involving an open-ended survey designed to gather foundational insights from participants. They will be prompted to clarify 2 main aspects: identify the target populations of SP (i.e., those who are expected to benefit more from SP), the specific methodologies used and tools to assess their effectiveness, and the role, qualifications, skills, and training required of SPLW. Participants will have 2 weeks to complete the survey, with an additional 3-day extension provided for non-responders.

Data collected during this round will be synthesized and used to structure the content of the subsequent round.

The research team leaders will conduct a qualitative content analysis to analyze participants' responses. Two senior researchers, F.P. and D.K., will independently review and categorize the qualitative data to identify key themes. The analysis will be performed manually, following a systematic approach to ensure rigor and reliability.

The findings from this round will be used to develop a structured survey for the next round of the Delphi process. At the start of the next round, participants will receive an anonymized summary of the responses from this round, ensuring transparency and allowing for informed consensus-building in the subsequent phase.

Round 2 will take place between May and June 2025. Participants will evaluate the synthesized items from Round 1 through a structured survey. Each item will be rated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree". Items achieving 80% or greater agreement will be accepted as consensus. A free-text box will allow participants to provide additional comments or suggest refinements to the proposed items.

Round 3 is scheduled for July to August 2025 and will focus on finalizing the definitions of the role of SPLW, their education and training as well as the target population who is expected to benefit more from SP and the tools used to assess the effectiveness. Participants will rate their agreement using the same 5-point Likert scale. A consensus threshold of 80% agreement will be applied. Participants who rate definitions below the threshold will be encouraged to provide detailed feedback to inform potential refinement. Otherwise, if consensus is achieved, no further rounds will be necessary.

Data analysis

The data collected from the registration survey will be analyzed with IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows v. 29 (IBM Corp., Armonk, USA). Qualitative data will be presented for each survey item and analyzed through qualitative content analysis.³⁸

Quality and transparency

This study will be conducted and reported by the Conducting and REporting DElphi Studies (CREDES) guidelines.³⁹

Ethics

At all time, the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki of 1964, revised by the World Medical Association (WMA) in 2013 in Fortaleza (Brazil), will be followed. Compliance with the European Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council,

dated April 27, 2016, regarding the protection of individuals concerning the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data, will be always ensured.

All data included in the study will be anonymized and treated confidentially. In the database, participants will be identified only by a code, without including any information that could allow for their identification.

The data obtained in the study will not be transferred to 3rd parties outside the members of the research team of this study at any time. All implemented security measures will be ensured to be sufficient to prevent any breaches of data confidentiality and privacy. Under no circumstances will the research team members have access to participant identification, either directly or indirectly.

Once the study is complete, the research team reserves the right to use the anonymized database solely for scientific purposes (journal articles, scientific papers, book chapters, etc.). The research team will not be permitted to access, use, transfer, or publish the project's database under any circumstances.

This study has been reviewed and approved for ethical compliance to the Research Ethics Committee of the ID-IAP Jordi Gol Primary Care Research Institute in Catalonia, Spain: V2, 08/03/2025 – 01/04/2025.

Data protection

The Principal Investigator, Ferdinando Petrazzuoli, will be responsible for the data storage and handling (ferdinando.petrazzuoli@gmail.com). The anonymized raw data that will support the findings of this study will be available from the corresponding author, upon reasonable request.

Discussion

By engaging diverse stakeholders and utilizing a structured consensus methodology, this study addresses the variability and lack of clarity surrounding the SPLW role, education, skills, and training across Europe, providing a unified framework that can inform research, policy and practice. Clarification and agreement on the target populations of SP (i.e., those who are expected to benefit more from SP), along with the methods and tools used for outcome evaluation, are also among the intended outcomes.

The findings of this Delphi study are expected to extend beyond conceptual clarification. By establishing consensus on the role, education and training of SPLWs, as well as the target populations and assessment tools, the results will inform the development of practical guidelines for health policy, educational curricula and clinical protocols. Specifically, they may inform national and regional policies on workforce development, serve as the basis for designing standardized educational curricula for SPLWs,^{4,7} and support clinicians in making more targeted referrals.⁸

Moreover, the recommendations developed through this process will be adaptable across diverse European healthcare systems^{24–26} – whether centralized, decentralized or in developmental stages – facilitating context-sensitive adoption. Finally, the consensus definitions and frameworks may facilitate the design of future comparative and interventional studies evaluating the effectiveness of SP,^{2,3} thereby strengthening its evidence base and promoting integration into holistic models of care.

The Delphi method has distinct strengths make it particularly suited for this endeavor.⁴⁰ Its core features – participant anonymity, iterative rounds of questioning and structured feedback between rounds – help minimize bias and encourage independent and thoughtful contributions from experts. The flexibility of this approach allows for the integration of diverse perspectives on complex topics, such as SP, where consensus must be built across varied healthcare systems and cultural context.^{29,34} Furthermore, using an online platform ensures geographic inclusivity and logistical feasibility, allowing experts from across Europe and beyond to participate without the constraints of physical meetings.

Limitations

Despite its strengths, the Delphi technique is not without limitations. It is known to be resource-intensive and time-consuming, requiring careful management to ensure the process remains efficient and that panel attrition is minimized. This study employs regular reminder emails, clearly defined timelines and engaging communication strategies to sustain participant engagement over all 3 rounds. Another challenge is the lack of standardized guidelines in literature regarding the Delphi process, particularly in determining what constitutes expert status and consensus thresholds. This protocol has addressed these concerns through adherence to the CREDES guidelines, which provide a structured approach to mitigate variability and ensure methodological rigor.³⁹ We also acknowledge other potential limitations, which are common to all Delphi studies, such as the risk of participants dropping out in later rounds or the overrepresentation of certain occupational groups or countries.

Conclusions

This Delphi study constitutes an important step toward establishing a shared conceptual and operational framework for SP in European primary care. By achieving expert consensus on the role, qualifications and training of SPLWs, as well as identifying appropriate target populations and tools for outcome assessment, the study will generate practical recommendations applicable across diverse healthcare systems. The findings are expected to support the systematic integration of SP into patient-centered and community-oriented

models of care, enhance the coherence of future research, and inform educational and policy development. In doing so, this work addresses key gaps in the standardization and implementation of SP across Europe.

Use of AI and AI-assisted technologies

Not applicable.

ORCID iDs

Ferdinando Petrazzuoli <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1058-492X>
 Josep Vidal-Alaball <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3527-4242>
 Joyce Kenkre <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2067-9001>
 Thomas Kloppe <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2368-8333>
 Sinah Evers <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5399-3355>
 Hendrik Napierala <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1542-2877>
 Jean-Pierre Jacquet <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6377-7728>
 Wolfram J. Herrmann <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9505-4911>
 Natasa Mrduljaš-Đujić <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0339-4354>
 Andrea Neculau <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4031-5694>
 Katerina Javorska <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1810-2668>
 David Halata <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4629-2232>
 Miriam Dolan <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0922-7290>
 Joanne Robins <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5786-9108>
 Patrick Ouvrard <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7148-3922>
 Juan Manuel Mendive <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8095-7707>
 Carmen López Fando <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2989-5106>
 Jane Randall-Smith <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5627-0726>
 Erwin Rebhandl <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2851-1974>
 Sara Paternoster <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7273-3898>
 Hans Thulesius <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3785-5630>
 Sian Brand <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2118-9534>
 Gindrovel Dumitra <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8982-9645>
 Donata Kurpas <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6996-8920>

References

1. Vidovic D, Reinhardt GY, Hammerton C. Can social prescribing foster individual and community well-being? A systematic review of the evidence. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(10):5276. doi:10.3390/ijerph18105276
2. Napierala H, Krüger K, Kuschick D, Heintze C, Herrmann WJ, Holzinger F. Social prescribing: Systematic review of the effectiveness of psychosocial community referral interventions in primary care. *Int J Integr Care*. 2022;22(3):11. doi:10.5334/ijic.6472
3. Cooper M, Avery L, Scott J, et al. Effectiveness and active ingredients of social prescribing interventions targeting mental health: A systematic review. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(7):e060214. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-060214
4. Brown RCH, Mahtani K, Turk A, Tierney S. Social prescribing in National Health Service primary care: What are the ethical considerations? *Milbank Q*. 2021;99(3):610–628. doi:10.1111/1468-0009.12516
5. Husk K, Blockley K, Lovell R, et al. What approaches to social prescribing work, for whom, and in what circumstances? A realist review. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2020;28(2):309–324. doi:10.1111/hsc.12839
6. Kim JE, Lee YL, Chung MA, et al. Effects of social prescribing pilot project for the elderly in rural area of South Korea during COVID-19 pandemic. *Health Sci Rep*. 2021;4(3):e320. doi:10.1002/hsr2.320
7. National Health Service (NHS). NHS long term workforce plan. London, UK: National Health Service (NHS); 2023. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/nhs-long-term-workforce-plan>. Accessed April 22, 2025.
8. Kiely B, Croke A, O'Shea M, et al. Effect of social prescribing link workers on health outcomes and costs for adults in primary care and community settings: A systematic review. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(10):e062951. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2022-062951
9. Wildman JM, Moffatt S, Steer M, Laing K, Penn L, O'Brien N. Service-users' perspectives of link worker social prescribing: A qualitative follow-up study. *BMC Public Health*. 2019;19(1):98. doi:10.1186/s12889-018-6349-x

10. Sandhu S, Lian T, Drake C, Moffatt S, Wildman J, Wildman J. Intervention components of link worker social prescribing programmes: A scoping review. *Health Social Care Community*. 2022;30(6):e3761–e3774. doi:10.1111/hsc.14056
11. Frostick C, Bertotti M. The frontline of social prescribing: How do we ensure link workers can work safely and effectively within primary care? *Chronic Illn*. 2021;17(4):404–415. doi:10.1177/1742395319882068
12. Hayes S, Sharman L, McNamara N, Dingle G. Link workers' and clients' perspectives on how social prescribing offers a social cure for loneliness. *J Health Psychol*. 2025;30(7):1624–1637. doi:10.1177/13591053241274090
13. Hazeldine E, Gowan G, Wigglesworth R, Pollard J, Asthana S, Husk K. Link worker perspectives of early implementation of social prescribing: A 'Researcher-in-Residence' study. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2021; 29(6):1844–1851. doi:10.1111/hsc.13295
14. Moore C, Unwin P, Evans N, Howie F. "Winging it": An exploration of the self-perceived professional identity of social prescribing link workers. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2023;2023:488615. doi:10.1155/2023/8488615
15. Mulholland J, Galway K, O'Hare L, Bertotti M, Gildea A. The Social Prescribing Link Worker: Clarifying the role to harness potential. A scoping review. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2025;2025(1):394123. doi:10.1155/hsc/4394123
16. Rhodes J, Bell S. "It sounded a lot simpler on the job description": A qualitative study exploring the role of social prescribing link workers and their training and support needs (2020). *Health Soc Care Community*. 2021;29(6):e338–e347. doi:10.1111/hsc.13358
17. Spencer LH, Lynch M, Makanjuola A. Qualifications and training needs of social prescribing link workers: An explorative study. *Lancet*. 2022;400(Suppl 1):S79. doi:10.1016/s0140-6736(22)02289-9
18. Turk A, Tierney S, Hogan B, Mahtani KR, Pope C. A meta-ethnography of the factors that shape link workers' experiences of social prescribing. *BMC Med*. 2024;22(1):280. doi:10.1186/s12916-024-03478-w
19. Welsh Government. National framework for social prescribing. Cardiff, UK: Welsh Government; 2023. <https://www.gov.wales/sites/default/files/pdf-versions/2024/1/2/1705399866/national-framework-social-prescribing.pdf>. Accessed April 22, 2025.
20. Linari A. Social prescribing: A means for combining social and health care? [doctoral thesis]. Milan, Italy: Polytechnic University of Milan; 2021. <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/179454>. Accessed April 22, 2025.
21. Husk K, Elston J, Gradinger F, Callaghan L, Asthana S. Social prescribing: Where is the evidence? *Br J Gen Pract*. 2019;69(678):6–7. doi:10.3399/bjgp19x700325
22. Surugiu R, Iancu MA, Lăcătuș AM, et al. Unveiling the presence of social prescribing in Romania in the context of sustainable healthcare: A scoping review. *Sustainability*. 2023;15(15):11652. doi:10.3390/su15111652
23. González JC, Braddick F, Schwartz Fields H, Segura Garcia L, Colom Farran J. Los retos de la prescripción social en la Atención Primaria de Catalunya: la percepción de los profesionales. *Comunidad*. 2016; 2(18):7. https://comunidad.semfyc.es/wp-content/uploads/Comunidad_-_Los-retos-de-la-prescripci%C3%B3n-social-en-la-Atenci%C3%B3n-Primaria-de-Catalunya_la-percepci%C3%B3n-de-los-profesionales.pdf. Accessed April 22, 2025.
24. Herrmann JW, Laker K, Napierala H. Challenges and opportunities for social prescribing in Germany: Policy and methodological perspectives. In: Bertotti M, ed. *Social Prescribing Policy, Research and Practice*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing; 2024:101–113. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-52106-5_7
25. Morse DF, Sandhu S, Mulligan K, et al. Global developments in social prescribing. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2022;7(5):e008524. doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2022-008524
26. Kurpas D, Mendive JM, Vidal-Alaball J, et al. European perspective on how social prescribing can facilitate health and social integrated care in the community. *Int J Integr Care*. 2023;23(2):13. doi:10.5334/ijic.7636
27. Baska A, Kurpas D, Kenkre J, et al. Social prescribing and lifestyle medicine: A remedy to chronic health problems? *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(19):10096. doi:10.3390/ijerph181910096
28. Chalmers J, Armour M. The Delphi technique. In: Liamputtong P, ed. *Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences*. Singapore: Springer Singapore; 2019:715–735. doi:10.1007/978-981-10-5251-4_99
29. Niederberger M, Spranger J. Delphi technique in health sciences: A map. *Front Public Health*. 2020;8:457. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2020.00457
30. Muhl C, Mulligan K, Bayoumi I, Ashcroft R, Godfrey C. Establishing internationally accepted conceptual and operational definitions of social prescribing through expert consensus: A Delphi study. *BMJ Open*. 2023;13(7):e070184. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2022-070184
31. Muhl C, Mulligan K, Bayoumi I, Ashcroft R, Godfrey C. Establishing internationally accepted conceptual and operational definitions of social prescribing through expert consensus: A Delphi study protocol. *Int J Integr Care*. 2023;23:3. doi:10.5334/ijic.6984
32. Frey BB, ed. *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation*. Thousand Oaks, USA: SAGE Publications; 2018. doi:10.4135/9781506326139
33. Barrett D, Heale R. What are Delphi studies? *Evid Based Nurs*. 2020; 23(3):68–69. doi:10.1136/ebnurs-2020-103303
34. Puig A, Adams C. Delphi technique. In: Frey BB, ed. *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Educational Research, Measurement, and Evaluation*. Thousand Oaks, USA: SAGE Publications; 2018. doi:10.4135/9781506326139.n190
35. Metzelthin SF, Rostgaard T, Parsons M, Burton E. Development of an internationally accepted definition of reablement: A Delphi study. *Ageing Soc*. 2022;42(3):703–718. doi:10.1017/s0144686x20000999
36. Campbell KA, Wood JN, Lindberg DM, Berger RP. A standardized definition of near-fatal child maltreatment: Results of a multidisciplinary Delphi process. *Child Abuse Negl*. 2021;112:104893. doi:10.1016/j.chiabu.2020.104893
37. Esfandiari E, Chudyk AM, Grover S, et al. Social Prescribing Outcomes for Trials (SPOT): Protocol for a modified Delphi study on core outcomes. *PLoS One*. 2023;18(5):e0285182. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0285182
38. Mayring P. *Qualitative Content Analysis: A Step-by-Step Guide*. Thousand Oaks, USA: SAGE Publications; 2021. ISBN: 978-1-5297-0197-5, 978-1-5297-0198-2.
39. Jünger S, Payne SA, Brine J, Radbruch L, Brearley SG. Guidance on Conducting and REporting DELphi Studies (CREDES) in palliative care: Recommendations based on a methodological systematic review. *Palliat Med*. 2017;31(8):684–706. doi:10.1177/0269216317690685
40. Savic LC, Smith AF. How to conduct a Delphi consensus process. *Anaesthesia*. 2023;78(2):247–250. doi:10.1111/anae.15808